

APPENDICES TO

Standardizing Course Assessment in Competency-Based Education: An Experience Report at a Chilean University

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Abstract

We examine the implementation of Competency-Based Education (CBE) at the Pontifical Catholic University of Valparaíso (PUCV) in Chile, focusing on the challenges associated with assessment methods in measuring students' competencies accurately. To address these issues, we first introduce the C-A&M model, which aims to standardize and improve course evaluation. Then, two complementary studies are reported: a within-groups design involving 20 Engineering courses and a between-groups design assessing the perceptions of 109 instructors across various faculties, including Law, Philosophy, and Education. Findings indicate that CBE is not yet fully realized at PUCV, with considerable room for improvement in evaluation strategies, alignment of learning objectives with competencies, and synchronization of training activities. However, the implementation of the C-A&M model led to significant enhancements in these areas, providing evidence of its effectiveness in advancing CBE practices.

Keywords: Competency-Based Education, Assessment Model, Course Structuring, Systematic Evaluation.

Appendix A. Rubric to assess CBE implementation in university courses

Tables [A.1](#) - [A.4](#) summarize the rubric we used to evaluate the CBE implementation in the courses that participated in S1.

Criteria for Assessing Curricular Coherence					
Competencies	Level				
	5 - Very High	4 - High	3 - Medium	2 - Low	1 - Very Low
1. Quality (c_quality)	Competencies are specific, concrete, and easy to understand.	Competencies are mostly specific and concrete, although some may require further interpretation.	Competencies are understandable, although some may be vague or general.	Competencies are unclear and require significant interpretation.	Competencies are ambiguous and difficult to understand.
2. Structure (c_structure)	Each competency is formulated following the structure: Verb (action) + Object (content) + Condition (contextual, professional, attitudinal) + Purpose (contextual, professional, attitudinal). Considerations: (i) Uses only one verb that accurately describes the action; (ii) The verb's taxonomy is appropriate and matches the competency level; (iii) The object is clearly identified with the action; (iv) The condition is clear and specific; and (v) The purpose clearly describes the goal the competency aims to achieve.	Most competencies are well-structured with a clear verb, defined object, specific condition, and understandable purpose. Considerations: (i) Uses a single verb, although it may sometimes lack precision; (ii) The verb's taxonomy is generally appropriate and matches the competency level; (iii) The object is identified in most cases; (iv) The condition is clear in most instances; and (v) The purpose is understandable and describes the competency's goal.	Competencies follow the basic structure but may have multiple verbs or lack clarity in some elements. Considerations: (i) May use more than one verb or a verb that does not precisely describe the action; (ii) The verb's taxonomy may be appropriate but not always suited to the competency level; (iii) The object may not be clearly identified in some cases; (iv) The condition may be vague or nonspecific; and (v) The purpose may not clearly describe the competency's goal.	Competencies do not consistently follow the recommended structure, with multiple verbs or a significant lack of clarity. Considerations: (i) Uses multiple verbs or imprecise verb; (ii) The verb's taxonomy may not be appropriate for the competency level; (iii) The object may be difficult to identify; (iv) The condition is vague or completely missing; and (v) The purpose does not describe the goal of the competency.	Competencies do not follow the recommended structure, with imprecise or absent verbs and objects, and unclear conditions and purposes. Considerations: (i) Uses multiple or inappropriate verbs; (ii) The verb's taxonomy is not appropriate; (iii) The object is difficult to identify or absent; (iv) The condition is vague or completely missing; and (v) The purpose does not describe the goal of the competency.
3. Competency Components (c_components)	Clearly identifies the conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal components (C, P, A) required to develop the competency.	Most competencies include conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal components (C, P, A), although some may not be fully developed.	Competencies include some conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal components (C, P, A) but are not fully identified or developed.	Competencies include few conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal components (C, P, A) and are poorly developed.	Competencies lack conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal components (C, P, A) and are either absent or undeveloped.

Table A.1: Rubric for Assessing Curricular Coherence in Relation to the Competencies' Dimension.

Criteria for Assessing Curricular Coherence		Level				
Learning Outcomes	5 - Very High	4 - High	3 - Medium	2 - Low	1 - Very Low	
1. Quality (lo_quality)	Learning Outcomes (LOs) are specific, relevant, measurable, and achievable within the course duration.	Most LOs are specific, relevant, measurable, and achievable within the course duration, although some may be less precise.	LOs are mostly relevant and measurable but may not be completely specific or achievable within the course duration.	LOs are vague or general and may not be entirely measurable or achievable within the course duration.	LOs are ambiguous, irrelevant, or unmeasurable and are not achievable within the course duration.	
2. Structure (lo_structure)	Each LO is formulated following the structure: Verb (action) + Object (content) + Condition (contextual, professional, attitudinal) + Purpose (contextual, professional, attitudinal). Considerations: (i) Uses a verb that accurately describes an observable and measurable action, appropriate for the taxonomic level required by the competency; (ii) The learning object is clearly identified; (iii) The “verb + object” combination clearly identifies the conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal components (C, P, A) that the LO aims to develop; (iv) The quality condition is very clear and specific, enabling the evaluation of the achieved performance; and (v) The LO’s purpose is clear, specific, and well-articulated.	The majority of LOs are well-formulated, with a clear verb, defined object, specific condition, and understandable purpose. Considerations: (i) Uses a verb that appropriately describes an observable and measurable action, though there may be slight variability in taxonomic level; (ii) The learning object is mostly identified; (iii) The “verb + object” combination generally identifies the C, P, A components, though some may be less clear; (iv) The quality condition is clear in most cases, though some ambiguity may exist; and (v) The purpose is clear and well-articulated in most cases.	LOs follow the basic structure but may include multiple verbs or lack clarity in some elements. Considerations: (i) Uses a verb describing an observable action, though it may lack precision at the taxonomic level; (ii) The learning object is present but may not be entirely clear; (iii) The “verb + object” combination sometimes identifies the C, P, A components of the competency but may lack clarity; (iv) The quality condition is generally present but may be vague or less specific; and (v) The purpose is understandable but may not be fully articulated.	LOs inconsistently follow the recommended structure, with multiple verbs or a significant lack of clarity. Considerations: (i) Uses imprecise verbs or multiple verbs that complicate precise measurement; (ii) The learning object may be difficult to identify; (iii) The “verb + object” combination rarely identifies the C, P, A components of the competency; (iv) The quality condition is vague and not specific; and (v) The purpose is unclear or poorly articulated.	LOs do not follow the recommended structure, with imprecise or absent verbs and objects, and lack clear conditions and purposes. Considerations: (i) Does not use precise verbs to describe observable actions; (ii) The learning object is hard to identify or absent; (iii) The “verb + object” combination does not identify the C, P, A components of the competency; (iv) The quality condition is absent or completely vague; and (v) The purpose is unclear and not articulated.	
3. Alignment (lo_alignment)	Each LO is explicitly related to: (i) The competency it contributes to; (ii) The course’s contents and formative activities; and (iii) The evaluation tools, allowing individualized measurement.	Most LOs are related to: (i) The competency they contribute to; (ii) The course’s contents and formative activities; and (iii) The evaluation tools, allowing individualized measurement, though some may need adjustments.	Some LOs are related to: (i) The competency they contribute to; (ii) The course’s contents and formative activities; and (iii) The evaluation tools, though the relationship may be partial or unclear.	Few LOs are related to: (i) The competency they contribute to; (ii) The course’s contents and formative activities; and (iii) The evaluation tools, with minimal or unclear relationships.	LOs are not related to: (i) The competency they should contribute to; (ii) The course’s contents and formative activities; and (iii) The evaluation tools, with absent or irrelevant relationships.	

Table A.2: Rubric for Assessing Curricular Coherence in Relation to the Learning Outcomes’ Dimension.

Criteria for Assessing Curricular Coherence						
Content & Training Activities		Level				
		5 - Very High	4 - High	3 - Medium	2 - Low	1 - Very Low
1. Relevance (cta_relevance)	The thematic units are highly relevant and directly related to the course context, addressing topics comprehensively and in an up-to-date manner.	All learning outcomes are comprehensively covered through the content and training activities, with no gaps or unaddressed areas.	Most of the thematic units are relevant to the course context and adequately address the main topics.	The thematic units are mostly relevant, but some may not be fully aligned with the course context or may be less pertinent.	The thematic units have limited relevance to the course context, with topics that may not be entirely pertinent or current.	The thematic units are irrelevant to the course context, with topics that are not aligned with the course needs.
2. Coverage (cta_coverage)			Most learning outcomes are well covered by the content and training activities, though there may be minor areas that are not fully addressed.	Coverage of learning outcomes is generally adequate, but there may be gaps or areas not fully addressed by the content and activities.	Coverage of learning outcomes is incomplete, with several areas not adequately addressed by the content and training activities.	Learning outcomes are not adequately covered by the content and training activities, with major gaps or unaddressed areas.
3. Sequence (cta_sequence)		The content and activities are presented in a logical and coherent order that facilitates understanding and allows for progressive and seamless learning.	The content and activities are presented in a mostly logical order that facilitates understanding and progressive learning, with some minor inconsistencies.	The content and activities follow a sequence that facilitates learning to some extent, but there may be mismatches or a lack of fluency in some parts.	The content and activities are presented in an order that hinders understanding and progressive learning, with significant mismatches in sequence.	The content and activities are presented in a disorganized order that prevents understanding and progressive learning.
4. Alignment (cta_alignment)		Each unit and training activity is clearly related to one or more established learning outcomes, ensuring complete alignment.	Most units and training activities are related to the established learning outcomes, though the relationship may not always be fully explicit.	Some units and training activities are related to the established learning outcomes, but the relationship is not always clear or explicit.	Few units and training activities are related to the established learning outcomes, and the relationship is unclear or absent.	There is no clear relationship between the units and training activities and the established learning outcomes, with alignment completely absent.

Table A.3: Rubric for Assessing Curricular Coherence in Relation to the Content and Training Activities' Dimension.

Criteria for Assessing Curricular Coherence		Level				
Evaluation Plan		5 - Very High	4 - High	3 - Medium	2 - Low	1 - Very Low
1. Coverage (ep_coverage)	The assessment tools comprehensively cover all the Learning Outcomes (LOs) of the course explicitly and completely.	Most of the assessment tools cover all the LOs of the course explicitly, although there may be some minor areas that are not fully covered.	The assessment tools cover most of the LOs of the course, but there may be some gaps or areas that are not fully addressed.	The assessment tools cover only some areas of the LOs of the course, with several significant gaps.	The assessment tools do not explicitly cover the LOs of the course, with large gaps in coverage.	
2. Assessment Tools (ep_ats)	The selected assessment tools are highly relevant to the Competency-Based Assessment (CBA) context, promoting the use of authentic assessments whenever necessary.	The assessment tools are generally suitable for the CBA context, with effective promotion of authentic assessments in most cases.	The assessment tools are generally suitable for the CBA context, but the use of authentic assessments may not be consistent in all cases.	The assessment tools are only partially relevant to the CBA context, with limited use of authentic assessments.	The assessment tools are not relevant to the CBA context and do not promote the use of authentic assessments.	
3. Achievement Indicators (ep_achievement_indicators)	Contains a detailed evaluation scheme based on achievement indicators that allows for precise assessment of each LO of the course.	The evaluation scheme contains achievement indicators that allow for the assessment of most LOs of the course, although some indicators may need adjustments.	The evaluation scheme contains achievement indicators that allow for the assessment of most LOs, but there may be a lack of detail in some indicators.	The evaluation scheme contains basic achievement indicators that allow for the assessment of some LOs, but there is a lack of detail or clarity in many indicators.	The evaluation scheme lacks adequate achievement indicators and does not allow for effective assessment of the LOs of the course.	
4. Assessment Rubrics (ep_rubrics)	The assessment rubrics are clear, consistent, and aligned with the defined achievement indicators for each LO, providing precise guidance for assessment.	The assessment rubrics are mostly clear and consistent with the achievement indicators, although there may be some areas where alignment is not completely precise.	The assessment rubrics are understandable and aligned with the achievement indicators, but they may have some inconsistencies or lack of clarity in some aspects.	The assessment rubrics are vague or inconsistent with the achievement indicators, making precise assessment of the LOs difficult.	The assessment rubrics are absent, inconsistent, or not aligned with the achievement indicators, making adequate assessment of the LOs difficult.	

Table A.4: Rubric for Assessing Curricular Coherence in Relation to the Evaluation Plan' Dimension.

Appendix B. Questionnaire to test C-A&M impact on implementing CBE in university courses

This appendix includes the questionnaire we used in S2 to check C-A&M's impact on implementing CBE in university courses. In particular, the questionnaire aimed to examine the following five dimensions described in Section ??:

- Coherence (Items 6-10 in the questionnaire).
- Exercises (Items 11-17).
- Feedback (Items 18-23).
- Alignment (Items 24-33).
- Assessment (Items 34-46).

Letter of introduction Dear instructor,

This questionnaire is designed to gather your opinion on the factors influencing the implementation of Competency-Based Education (CBE) in university courses. Please answer the following questions based on your own perception. Some questions may appear similar, but there are important differences between them. If you teach several courses, focus your responses on only one course, preferably the one in which you feel more involved.

Please be assured that your answers will remain anonymous, and confidentiality will be maintained. The results will be used primarily for academic purposes. If you have any questions about the process, please contact Hector Vargas at hector.vargas@pucv.cl or Emanuel Arredondo at emanuel.arredondo@uv.cl.

Thank you for your participation.

Questionnaire items:

1. How old are you?: _____
2. What is your gender?
 - Male.
 - Female.
 - Other one.
3. What is your academic degree?
 - Bachelor's degree.
 - Master's degree.
 - PhD.
4. In which faculty do you regularly teach?: _____

5. Have you used the Competency Assessment and Monitoring framework (C-A&M) in your course?: Yes No

Please rate from 1 to 10 the extent to which you agree with the following statements about your course syllabus (1 totally disagree, 10 absolutely agree):

6. The existing pedagogical relationship between Competencies and Learning Outcomes is consistent: _____
7. The contents addressed in the course are consistent with the Learning Outcomes: _____
8. The Learning Outcomes are written in a way that allows for measurement: _____
9. The assessment conducted in the subject evaluates the learning outcomes of the course: _____
10. The chosen weights are appropriate for the assessment of competencies: _____

Thinking about the development of the strategies and evaluation tools used in your course, please rate from 1 to 10 your level of agreement with the following statements (1 totally disagree, 10 absolutely agree):

11. The exercises or study cases presented in the assessment allow for practical application: _____
12. The exercises or study cases allow for better application of what was learned in class: _____
13. The existing pedagogical relationship between Competencies and Learning Outcomes is consistent: _____
14. The exercises or study cases presented are contextualized to the professional field: _____
15. The exercises or study cases challenge students with work-related scenarios: _____
16. The exercises or study cases are designed in relation to the professional activities of students: _____
17. The exercises or study cases present situations that occur in the professional field: _____
18. The given feedback allows students to learn from their mistakes: _____
19. The given feedback allows students to improve their learning: _____
20. The given feedback enables students to understand which areas they need to focus on: _____
21. The evaluation provides constructive feedback to help students understand their mistakes and what they need to improve. _____
22. The given feedback helps students identify the areas they need to improve: _____

23. The review time for assessments should not exceed two weeks: _____
24. The course is planned coherently with the learning outcomes: _____
25. The course is planned considering the diversity of students: _____
26. The course is planned considering the competency-based approach: _____
27. The course employs methodologies that promote the development of competencies in students: _____
28. The course employs methodologies that allow for the practical application of what is covered in class: _____
29. The course integrates methodologies so that students are the protagonists of their learning: _____
30. The assessment proposed in the course is consistent with competency-based assessment: _____
31. The assessment developed allows for the practical application of what is covered in class: _____
32. The assessment is consistent with the learning outcomes of the course: _____
33. The assessment is consistent with the methodologies used in the course: _____
34. The criteria used in the rubrics are consistent with the learning outcomes: _____
35. The levels of achievement are adequately described: _____
36. The levels of achievement are constructed in an increasing/decreasing manner _____
37. The levels of achievement properly guide students regarding what is expected for each criterion: _____
38. The levels of achievement are achievable for students: _____
39. The levels of achievement allow for evidence of the progressive development of a competency: _____
40. The rubrics are available to all students: _____
41. The rubrics are available in the course's virtual classroom: _____
42. The rubrics are used for grading student assessments: _____
43. The rubrics are used to provide feedback to students: _____
44. The rubrics are presented to students before each evaluation: _____
45. Each rubric's content is clearly described to the students: _____
46. The rubric goals are explained in detail to the students: _____